

Research Consortium on
Education and Peacebuilding

The Role of Education in
Peacebuilding
Country Report:
South Africa

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April 2016

Executive Summary

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This report explores three interrelated areas tied to the role of education in promoting social cohesion in South Africa. They include: the integration of education into the country’s social cohesion policies and processes (RA 1); the role of teachers in building social cohesion (RA 2); and the role of formal and non-formal education programmes focusing on youth and social cohesion (RA 3). The report is part of the work of the Research Consortium on Education and Peace Building and is supported by UNICEF’s Peacebuilding, Education and Advocacy (PBEA) programme.

Throughout the report social cohesion is understood as societal rather than individual property, based on the need to promote positive relationships, trust, solidarity, inclusion, collectivity, and common purpose within society. This is also because social cohesion has important social justice and equity dimensions, and as such is deemed to exist within the structural, inter-personal, and inter-group domains. Social cohesion in South Africa is further linked to the production of an aspirational society with strong aspects of social inclusion, social capital, and social mobility (see OECD 2012). As such, the term is used interchangeably with peacebuilding, as done by the UNICEF PBEA, as a way of reflecting the different local country context. The report conceives of the promotion of social cohesion as the extent to which patterns of inequality associated with injustice are disrupted in South Africa, and the extent to which redistribution, recognition, representation and reconciliation are effected.

The report offers two kinds of findings that emerged from the report. The first level of findings highlight the different ways in which social cohesion issues have been addressed, understood, and approached in South Africa since 1994. The second level of findings reports on key issues in the study that emerged in relation to policy, teachers, and youth.

Social Cohesion

1. Efforts to foster social cohesion in South Africa are firmly rooted in a history of colonialism and apartheid that not only fractured social identities along the lines of race and ethnicity, but solidified them in unequal relations that continue to separate the population across unequally resourced spatial areas. This meant that after the elections of 1994, dealing with issues of equity, redress, and social cohesion was the core priority of the democratically elected government. Disconcertingly however, more than two decades after the end of apartheid, the legacies of many past policies remain and much of the physical landscape of apartheid has undergone very little change. More problematically, inequalities have become normalized and accepted almost as a given within policy pronouncements, while a mix of previous race and social privilege have reconfigured to become the main basis of persistent discrimination. As such, the scars of a racially segregated school system under apartheid continue to retain their hold over current schools, with a small number of well-resourced schools located in urban areas and accessed by the privileged minority, while poorly-resourced schools mainly cater for black (all those disadvantaged under apartheid) learners.

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Notwithstanding an explicit focus by the ANC government since 1994 to redress the various kinds of inequalities and to foster effective and meaningful structural change, there needs to be more overt agreements about what would constitute meaningful change in South Africa, and attention needs to be given to its implementation. Context matters for social cohesion strategies, and one-size-fits-all approaches are unlikely to succeed.

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2. There are also several binding constraints on the attainment and promotion of social cohesion and the facilitation of agency in South Africa. These include the large number of socially conditioning structural features that the new ANC government had to contend with from 1994. Many of these features could not be addressed because of the particular form that the transition took, where neither the oppressive ruling government nor the opposition forces could secure a decisive military victory in ending their conflict; thus leading to a negotiated settlement. Within the negotiated settlement, the focus on securing liberal rights alongside a commitment to redress meant that social cohesion was mainly expressed in the symbolic Coats of Arms as ‘Unity with Diversity’ and in popular discourse as the ‘Rainbow Nation’. A further constraint has been the raft of progressive policies that have struggled to fully balance and address equity and redress needs within a governance environment where powers have already been devolved to local agents at different systemic levels (provinces, schools), and across which implementation differs widely. This has not been helped by a macro development trajectory that positions social cohesion and education within a very narrow growth agenda, in which economic growth in a liberal capitalist democracy is seen as the engine for social sector transformation.

As such, there needs to be greater national consensus on how to ensure that social cohesion initiatives are meaningful to all sectors and to all citizens, as well as on the aims of different initiatives and the kinds of values required to effect change. There needs to be specific, measurable and achievable targets and indicators that measure activities, programmes, and events, but this needs to be underpinned by a framework that challenges fixed and reified individual and group identities, accommodates approaches such as anti-racism and radical cosmopolitan citizenship, and locates belonging in contexts of social class and institutional determination.

“While government policies since 1994 have sought to redress the most obvious inequities of apartheid through the formal desegregation of schools, the equalising of expenditure, and in affirming the rights of individuals, the issue of access to education continues to be a national problem, especially around the operation of local level actors in a decentralised system of governance.”

3. While government policies since 1994 have sought to redress the most obvious inequities of apartheid through the formal desegregation of schools, the equalising of expenditure, and in affirming the rights of individuals, the issue of access to education continues to be a national problem, especially around the operation of local level actors in a decentralised system of governance. Because the policy framework after 1994 enabled strong assertive SGBs, particularly in wealthier schools, most schools have remained highly homogeneous in their student composition which has meant that social cohesion across different local community and class lines has struggled to gain traction. There is also limited movement of learners and teachers across homogenous school types which mitigates against cross-class and group solidarity in which there is proactive and willing sharing of resources.

There is a need for stronger proactive measures to erode group-based inequalities in order to achieve sustainable and durable social cohesion.

4. The notion of social cohesion in South Africa is a contested concept, both in policy and practice. On the one hand, there are those who advocate social cohesion as an awareness of the ‘other’ and for which interaction strategies are proffered. This is manifest in celebrations of different religious days and teaching that focuses on an understanding of different religions and groups,

cross-community camps, choral choirs, and mixed sport events. In this form, social cohesion is premised on largely intact, stable, and cohesive group and individual identities, with a focus on an awareness of how the 'other' lives, thinks, and practices. On the other hand, there are alternative conceptualisations of social cohesion that seek to build an egalitarian and communitarian society in which identity and belonging is destabilised and critiqued, and not taken for granted. In so doing, the focus is on how to balance difference with commonality, social class interest with cross-class solidarity, individual interest with societal imperatives, and loyalty and fidelity to the state with critical forms of citizenship. This approach to social cohesion relies on difference being destabilised and re-assembled in diverse ways, and thus social cohesion is seen as never final or complete, and requires continuous renewal.

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The manner in which education articulates with social integration and a push for greater equality needs closer attention so that initiatives like reading the preamble of the Constitution and having a visible flag are supported and further articulated in meaningful integration on sportsfields and civic environments and in the ways learners interact with each other across multiple spaces. Policy conclusions and recommendations need to approach social cohesion as both a process and an outcome.

5. The issue of education quality remains a serious challenge in South Africa, but should be separated from the affective needs of social cohesion. First, the consistent focus on literacy and numeracy, it must be recognised, is important in itself as good quality education for the poor is an important foundational element of creating the bond of solidarity, belonging and critical citizenship that is necessary for social cohesion. Second, social cohesion is an important education policy objective in and of itself.

By adopting an expanded notion of education quality in South Africa, responses to on-going physical and symbolic violence, xenophobia, and the denial of the rights of groups such as LGBTIQ (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Intersex, Queer people) and migrants and refugees, can lead to shifts in policy and practice and ensure that the affective goals in education are not de-legitimated in favour of a strategy which privileges 'litnum' (literacy and numeracy) goals. Every moment of positive social cohesion carries within it the possibility of new forms of exclusion.

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6. Inequality is perhaps the most profound characteristic of life in South Africa. All measures of inequality in South Africa reflect a growing divide between the rich and poor, and the employed and unemployed/unemployable. This inequality is historical, structural, and largely racialised. Inequality is relational to the extent that the rich, along with the wealthy and middle class group, will remain rich as long as the large African majority remain poor. Social cohesion and social justice as forms of meaningful belonging is difficult to conceive in such a highly unequal societal context. The existence of a two-tier, 'bifurcated' education system reflects widely differing and segmented experiences of belonging and interaction, which are key preconditions for social cohesion in society.

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Education is necessary to engender a more radical conception of social cohesion but cannot remedy all forms of inequity. Joined up, cross-sectoral interventions are needed that are coupled with inclusive national economic development growth plans and trajectories that promote social cohesion. This might, for example, include facilitating mixed-income residential neighbourhoods, or fostering community safety programmes and school safety programmes that promote increased social and community interaction in dangerous environments, or raising the status of African languages within schools to challenge the hegemonic status quo of English and Afrikaans.

7. Teacher agency and youth agency in South Africa is differentially conditioned by the contexts teachers and youth find themselves in. Firstly, social class and wealth determines much of the lived realities of individuals in South Africa, such as where they live, where they go to school, and who their friends are. These everyday experiences are overlaid by notions of race, gender, and geographical history that frame how social cohesion, if seen as belonging and solidarity, is approached. Secondly, institutions shape what student teachers as future agents of social cohesion experience. Notwithstanding the reconfiguration of higher education since 1994, the training of teachers in South Africa continues to reflect older modalities of institutional access, albeit in new gendered and class forms. Many teacher education providers still have the same profile of student teachers as in the past, which results in very differentiated understandings of, and approaches to, social cohesion for those in training. The agency of teachers and youth is enacted in spaces that remain segmented and separated, using tools that are shaped by their experiences and the institutions they attend, and in ways that invariably reflect what they have been taught.

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On the one hand, caution must therefore be exercised in replicating interventions that show promise for diverse and different contexts. On the other, there needs to be more proactive forms of redistribution within programmes that are not short-term strategic interventions. Social cohesion is both about psychological change as much as about structural change. There thus needs to be a greater focus on the principles of social justice to redress substantive rights that were denied to a majority-oppressed population, that sets out not to ‘level the playing field’, and rather to ‘change the game and the rules of the game’. In essence, this may require an approach to social cohesion founded in alternative economic growth and development paths and visions.

Research Area Findings

1. Policy

Policies in South Africa that seek to address social cohesion are broad in scope and deep in commitment. Yet, while much has been achieved at a high level by successive governments, it is the coordination of effective policies at decentralised levels and across different social spaces to engage citizens that has been lacking:

- A policy overload and coordination - Policy overload is often an outcome of a policy formulation process whereby new strategies and directions are added to an existing suite of policies. This often results in fragmentation and incoherence. Examples here include policy areas such as curriculum and governance that have passed through several amendments. Furthermore, policies also emanate from different divisions in government with particular policies being seen as 'silos'. Education policies for social cohesion as a cross cutting goal requires clear leadership and actor and stakeholder awareness and commitment. A technical review of existing policy is needed, noting areas of duplication and incoherence as a first stage in developing a focused and specific education strategy for effecting social cohesion in and through education.
- Translating policy into practice - The development of a progressive legal framework belies the fact that policy implementation has been inconsistent. Generating the political will to enforce policies and enhancing the capacity and willingness of those in the implementation front-line is necessary. Policies and interventions often have unintended consequences, and addressing conceptual and other inconsistencies in policies which militate against equity, such as the powers accorded to SGBs to control admission and the failure to enforce a fair fee exemptions policy, is a necessary precondition to improving implementation.
- Decentralised governance requires careful coordination and integration – The mediation of policies is, in the South African context, an outcome of the semi-federal education governance arrangement where provinces have scope to engage, positively and negatively, with policy aims. In many cases however decentralised governance has eroded efforts focused on bringing about equity and meaningful integration, making it difficult to attain durable peace and social cohesion.
- Policies to effect durable social cohesion should be underpinned by a shared understanding and approach coupled with effective monitoring mechanisms -Too often, policy mandates at provincial levels are not adequately funded, which then undermines the successful implementation of policies. It can often have outcomes like shortages of teachers or lead to a lack of textbooks, which negatively impact mainly deprived schools. It is always necessary when developing policies to ensure that there is adequate funding and monitoring to realise the targets and indicators of those policies, especially crucial policies like Outcome 14: Social Cohesion.
- Utilising policy spaces - The progressive raft of policies in education and beyond the sector has created the space for the public and communities to hold government to account. Chapter 9 institutions are an important part of the policy space for the needs and concerns of the poor and marginalised to be heard, and their rights protected. Utilising the spaces created by policy for citizens requires the strengthening of capacity of civil society organisations so that they can engage not only in policy monitoring but also policy formulation. Making better use of such institutions to protect and promote citizen rights will require intensifying their involvement in education, particularly in relation to social cohesion.

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2. Teachers

Teachers play pivotal roles in supporting social cohesion in schools. The success of these roles however is tied to key initiatives that have sought to strengthen teacher professionalism, and encourage trust and accountability amongst those within the teaching profession. Similarly, a number of initiatives have sought to ensure that teachers are well-trained, and that resources such as textbooks take into account the goals of social cohesion. There has also been a focus on creating access to continuing support and teacher development that allows for a more joined up approach to the supporting of teachers. However:

- The density of education policies in general and those which focus on social cohesion expect too much of teachers and schools. – It is not unreasonable to expect more from teachers in a society seeking to redress deep-seated structural inequities and overcome a long legacy of colonial oppression and segregation and apartheid. However, the key problem is often that change is mostly exercised in contexts informed by the divided and bifurcated nature of the education system where the majority of schools are arguably dysfunctional. Undoubtedly, the contextual realities in which teachers find themselves severely inhibit their agency. Policy implementation is contingent on the extent to which they reflect the contextual spaces teachers occupy. To this end attention should be paid to strengthening teacher involvement and participation in policy formulation about social cohesion, and in developing differentiated policy strategies (and support) for social cohesion that take into account the differing school contextual realities.
- Strengthening accountability measures to deal with violence in schools is necessary. The deep concern in South Africa at the levels of widespread violence within schools has tended to focus on how it undermines the environment necessary for effective teaching and learning, and less on the everyday effects it has on learners. Studies have shown, for example, that one in five secondary school learners experience forms of violence at school. Yet there remains a lack of political will to hold teachers accountable (to make certain learners safe) or to ensure that progressive legal frameworks are upheld or to ensure safe social contexts for learning. School-based and community-based violence is multi-dimensional and requires stakeholders that better understand the policies and can empathise with what they are trying to achieve.
- Involving key stakeholders in the development of explicit teacher workforce supply side measures is a key strategy - Interventions to redress the imbalances in teacher recruitment and deployment have increasingly been weighted to factor in educator requirements with respect to equity, access and redress. However, post provisioning norms and standards (PPNs) that act to measure this are invariably more narrowly resource-driven, and are increasingly framed by tight budget envelopes at provincial levels. This often leads to a negative impact on poorer schools, while wealthier schools are able to circumvent the model using their private resources. On the other hand, more explicit and consolidated supply driven measures such as the Funza Lushaka Bursary Program (FLBP) can in the medium term show its impact more positively on overall teacher supply, especially in areas of teacher shortage. The involvement of education districts and community-based teacher recruitment strategies, alongside simple and accurate timely information, may serve to further bolster and increase the effectiveness of this intervention.
- Trust and accountability measures require reinforcement and support to achieve the goals of social cohesion. It is critical to build a culture of trust in which teachers act as professional and active agents to uphold the codes of conduct

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and ethics that they agree to, and to enforce sanctions against teachers who transgress. The IQMS is a comprehensive, yet weakly co-ordinated, evaluation and accountability mechanism. The IQMS offers little support to the department to enable teachers to abide by accountability demands, and unequal resource distribution often places more demands on teachers who do not have the resources to follow through on recommendations. Simplified accountability mechanisms, with the buy-in of teachers, are needed. Similarly, the South African Council of Educators (SACE) is an important platform for the development of the professionalism of the teaching profession. However, communication with other important government departments is important to deal with issues such as teacher misconduct. Finally, SGBs while vital for democratic participation in school governance and community involvement have not been instrumental in minimising inequality. If SGBs are to fulfil their roles effectively they need to be in possession of better cultural capital and resources.

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- Preparing student teachers as agents of social cohesion and peace requires innovation and coherence - Case studies of initial teacher education programs suggest that additional support can be given to student teachers as they confront diversity in its fragmented forms during their learning experiences. In particular, empowering student teachers with approaches and tools to engage everyday diverse manifestations of racial and linguistic practices would empower them as agents of social cohesion and peace. Inequality and fragmentation lends itself to conflict and violence in as much as it does to respect and innovation. While data suggests that student teachers are committed to social cohesion notwithstanding their different backgrounds, more careful and innovative interventions are needed to enhance student teachers’ practical ‘cross-over’ teaching practicum experiences. Furthermore, programs need conceptual coherence to take account of issues of social cohesion in order for teachers to experience their initial teacher education as empowering, and to develop an expanded notion of professionalism within which they convert their potential.
- Supporting CPTD programs that deal with the pedagogies and values of social cohesion is a sustainable incentive for change - Case studies of interventions illustrate the need for CPTD programs that take into account teachers attitudes and possible prejudices. These illustrate that while such interventions might increase awareness of roles and responsibilities towards learners in their classroom, their sustainability depends on on-going support to ensure translation into positive classroom practice. Dialogue and consultation is needed to develop a common framework, and an understanding of how issues of social cohesion and teacher agency can be addressed in the content of initial and continuing professional development programmes. A strategy of foregrounding issues of teacher values and disposition in initial and continuing professional development programmes should be linked to measures to incentivise NGOs and other providers to provide on-going professional development for teachers - to capacitate them in understanding the pedagogies and values of social cohesion.
- Ensuring that curriculum and textbooks address the goals of peacebuilding and social cohesion requires a joined up approach -The context of the curriculum must deal with the drivers of societal fragmentation and inequality in South Africa including race, class, sexual orientation, gender and religion. Policies must also ensure that social cohesion as a curriculum imperative has a ‘carrier subject’ and is also mainstreamed across all subjects. A reconfiguring of the textbook review process such that issues of social cohesion feature more prominently in the review process, and in the textbook publishing process, is required. This needs to be accompanied by more open resource publications, particularly for resources and material addressing social cohesion.

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3. Youth

Youth operate in pivotal ways, both within schools and society. They can otherwise be agents of social transformation, troublemakers or security threats, or victims caught up in challenging contexts where they need protection or policy intervention. The nature of their roles is thus tied to key initiatives that provide a more collaborative approach that promote their agency, and recognise their diverse needs and challenges. In mobilising the skills, knowledge, and understanding of different groups of youth, and better linking the cultural, political, and economic aspects of their agency through both macro and micro interventions, the contributions of youth to social cohesion can be advanced. In so doing, there is a need to:

“When youth are not treated as assets to society it limits their capacity to take charge of their individual wellbeing.”

- Link up broad measures to address economic issues for youth - High levels of economic inequality and poverty in South Africa inflict severe constraints on youth and inform how they address issues of social cohesion. While programmes like the National Youth Service attempt to mitigate this by creating job opportunities, the small size and ambition of these initiatives, and the sheer size of the bigger economic problem, are such that a radical rethink on how to address this issue is needed.
- Take steps to intervene through the social services that protect youth - Addressing youth vulnerability requires concerted measures and shapes their understanding of social cohesion. Youth report extremely high levels of social challenges, including the high prevalence levels of HIV/Aids, sexual activity and teen pregnancy, maternal deaths, single parenting, and mental health problems, coupled with limited or non-existent availability or access to integrated health care and social services. To foster social solidarity and take the needs of youth seriously, much more needs to be done to intervene in the social challenges that they confront daily. Similarly, their constant everyday exposure to excessively high levels of physical (murder, assault and rape), gender-based violence, discrimination and exploitation and intergenerational-violence, needs to be systematically addressed as this in no uncertain terms shapes how they approach their lives.
- Promote the support systems and resources of communities for youth that are key to fostering social cohesion in society - Divisions across class, community, societal and cultural divides and the resultant low levels of social cohesion and integration that continue to characterise South African society are reinforced by low levels of positive parenting (including male role models), or substantive community support systems and resources in marginalised communities. The disillusionment of youth affects their levels of participation in political and civic structures, and alongside processes that are attached to poor service delivery, inaccessibility, and a lack of trust in officialdom (including the police), this tends to erode efforts to foster social cohesion.
- Build on the strengths of youth to bring about change - The key challenge for youth to act as agents of change is that current policy continues to frame youth in deficit terms. Policy treats youth as passive receivers of top-down and institutionalized solutions to their problems. When youth are not treated as assets to society it limits their capacity to take charge of their individual wellbeing. A number of lessons can be taken from established youth and community development initiatives, with their asset-based approach and their attempts to better understand individual youth and their respective needs both in schools and in everyday life.

The Research Consortium on Education and Peacebuilding

Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research (AISSR), University of Amsterdam

The AISSR Programme Group Governance and Inclusive Development (<http://aissr.uva.nl/programmegroups/item/governance-and-inclusive-development.html>) consists of an interdisciplinary team of researchers focusing on issues relating to global and local issues of governance and development. The Research Cluster Governance of Education, Development and Social Justice focuses on multilevel politics of education and development, with a specific focus on processes of peacebuilding in relation to socio-economic, political and cultural (in)justices. The research group since 2006 has maintained a particular research focus on education, conflict and peacebuilding, as part of its co-funded 'IS Academie' research project with the Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

Centre for International Education, University of Sussex

The Centre for International Education (CIE) (www.sussex.ac.uk/education/cie) was founded in 1989 on the premise that education is a basic human right that lies at the heart of development processes aimed at social justice, equity, social and civic participation, improved wellbeing, health, economic growth and poverty reduction. It is recognised as one of the premiere research centres working on education and international development in Europe. The Centre has also secured a prestigious UK ESRC/DFID grant to carry out research on the Role of Teachers in Peacebuilding in Conflict Affected Contexts, which aligns directly with the research strategy of the PBEA programme and will form part of the broader research partnership.

UNESCO Centre at Ulster University

Established in 2002 the UNESCO Centre (www.unescocentre.ulster.ac.uk) at the University of Ulster provides specialist expertise in education, conflict and international development. It builds on a strong track record of research and policy analysis related to education and conflict in Northern Ireland. Over the past ten years the UNESCO Centre has increasingly used this expertise in international development contexts, working with DFID, GIZ, Norad, Save the Children, UNESCO, UNICEF and the World Bank, providing research on education and social cohesion, the role of education in reconciliation and analysis of aid to education in fragile and conflict affected situations.

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